

Impacts of Globalisation on Internationalisation of Higher Education - A Review

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Abstract: Globalization and internationalization of higher education is an important but multifaceted phenomenon whose impact has multiple effects on world educational industry. This work is a review of the article: *Globalization and Higher Education: Eight Common Perceptions from University Leaders* [13]. We examine the implications of this dynamic relationship in consideration of these eight factors towards globalization of university education in the 21st century.

Keywords: Globalization, Internationalization, University, HEI, 21st Century.

1. INTRODUCTION

The term “globalization is generally used to refer to a complicated set of economic, political, and cultural factors. As a result of expanding world trade, nations and individuals experience greater economic and political interdependence (Wells et al, 1998). The effect of globalization of education affects each country in uniquely diverse ways. There is a dynamic relationship between internationalization and globalization of education that needs further exploration for the overall benefit of the global higher education institution. This could be nation-individual history based, priorities, tradition, or culture based. The author of the article Dr. Van R. Wood identifies and vividly outlines and clarifies some Common perceptions from University Leaders, eight of which has emanated from various opinions of some Higher Education Institutions (HIE) leaders in the United States. These have been spurred by a vision or philosophy transmitted from the highest levels of university leadership concerning the necessity and value of internationalization in globalization of education (Wood, Van R., 2007). In educational Context, globalization is primarily a perceived set of changes that include the shaping of new, global forms in culture, the media and technologies of communication that nations have to accept and follow in order to be able to embrace global competition and respond positively (Carnoy, 1999; Van Damm, 2001). Higher education systems, policies and institutions are being transformed by globalization, which is the widening, deepening and speeding up of worldwide interconnectedness (Held et al. 1999, p. 2). This was aptly captured in offering a definition for the term “globalization” in the context of Higher Education. In the article, globalization was perceived as a symbol of international system. International system would be futile without globalization. Rather than globalization represent an international System as the author highlighted, I would rather suppose globalization as the international system, shaping most societies today. The authors announce three principal factors which drive globalization viz technology, information and finance. These have their inherent positive and negative sides, having identified knowledge processing, and the ability to use knowledge in a worldwide arena critical to personal and societal advancement. The author specifies, and I concur that most observers believe that the ability to harness the good from globalization and avoid the bad lies in the cultivation of knowledge [14].

1.1. Definition (21st Century Institution):

From the author, according to Dr. John Heyl, “Every campus is different, so it depends on what environment you are in, what your strengths are, to whom you are trying to cater, and where you want to go. For example, the international student population at ODU was reported to have doubled over the last six years, and they believe this has come about because of the goals set for the university and the resulting international programs and initiatives that were developed. The author further states that if one provides a distinct and high quality product and backs it up with meaningful service, the rest will take care of itself, and that Institutions begin to be successful when they realize that globalization is not going away, but instead responsibly build a campus and community culture that embraces tolerance, interconnectivity and openness.”

2. MAIN IDEA

The writer opines that in a world-wide arena, personal and societal advancements not only hinge on knowledge but on having the ability to use knowledge. In the review, crucial and important questions were raised regarding what the role of higher education institutions in should be creating nurturing environments for promising individuals (Florida 2002, Friedman 2005). This is pertinent in the technologically advanced century in which the global community thrives. The goals of the higher education institutions should be that of responding to students, faculty and their communities by way of empowering them to prosper in the global interconnected society. It is apparent what the leaders of higher education institutions who should profess a common body of thoughts, wisdom and insights with respect to higher education and globalization, hence the need to for a year-long investigation. The article reveals eight common perceptions which are listed herein under: Thomas L. Friedman (2005) separates Globalization into three periods that go from the First Globalization (1482–1800), to the Second Globalization (1800 - 2000), and to the Third Globalization (2000 - to date). According to him, the First Globalization involved countries, the Second involved companies, and the Third is involving individual. In what follows we examine the eight common perceptions from university leaders as earlier stated in the abstract.

a. Dealing with Internationalization of Campus and Community:

The author sees these perceptions as both an opportunity as well as a challenge that must be dealt with Study results indicated that university leaders understand and embrace this point and feel an urgency to deal with it today. Key questions due to globalization of education under this perception include inter alia:

- (i) What kind of careers are emerging in today’s interconnected world, where are they emerging and how do we prepare our students and communities for them?
- (ii) How can our departments, schools and university achieve an enhanced international presence?
- (iii) How can institutions of higher education be positioned for success in today’s global environment and what role should local, regional, national and international partners play?
- (iv) What global trends, developments and related research topics are most important to our scholarly disciplines today, and how can we take advantage of such to create new knowledge in the future?

These provide the essential questions those in charge of programs, curricula and initiatives in global higher educational system the world over should be looking to solve.

b. Pursuing Vision Matters:

The article’s perspective of a great institution is that which is able to let the world know their purpose and vision about what they are and what they strive to be in future, and not just about an institution’s buildings and infrastructure which in itself is an essential requirement but are only part of success equation. The study reveals the position of university leaders regarding the responsibility of institutions of higher learning, and identifies them as follows:

- (a) Enlightening and preparing of their students
- (b) Enlightenment of their respective communities for the challenges and opportunities brought on by globalization
- (c) Being the major supplier of the intellectual human capital that communities need to survive and prosper in the era of globalization.

(d) From the article, the assertion of Former President Herman B. Wells of Indiana University - Bloomington is one that should be given serious considerations for purposes of implementation. In the words of President Herman B. Wells:

“The campus of Indiana University is not just in Bloomington, or even the state of Indiana; it encompasses the four corners of the globe. And our campus culture from the top echelons of leadership to the bottom rungs of entering first-year students must reflect this reality.”

This is a good measure and should be used as indicator of what a vision or philosophy of an institution should be because what an institution becomes tomorrow is in their seed of today. It is therefore clearly understood why the author sees in the eye of the realities of globalization in identifying the following as key:

- (a) Greater competition
- (b) Relentless pressures to innovate
- (c) New worldwide markets and production options,
- (d) Growing concerns over cultural and environmental degradation

Remark:

If these four points are tenaciously pursued, they would enable any Higher Education institution to achieve globalization. Any institution whose goal deviates from these may still exist but would not fit into the scheme of things in the 21st Century attainments of higher educational organizations, and as the author aptly captured it, and I quote, “Any entity that does not support an environment that attracts, sustains and retains creative, imaginative, and globally resourceful individuals will eventually fall behind”

c. Establishment of Broad Policies and Priorities:

Getting meaningful initiatives off the ground in any institution is predicated on broad-based “buy-ins,” beginning with the top university leadership, but also including deans and department heads at specific schools, directors of centers, individual faculty members, students, and the broader community-based leadership as well. The article contains that effective university leaders do not demand an embrace of the international arena at their institutions, what they do is establish broad policies and priorities related to innovative initiatives aimed at developing a global culture throughout their campus and community, and then let the creative entrepreneurs take over. Clearly stated policies and resulting priorities can lead to myriads of noteworthy international initiatives among the universities. These initiatives include exceptional visiting scholar support, unique degree and non-degree certification options, distinctive overseas study agendas, exclusive international internships, innovative student scholarships, part - time job options in the international arena; outstanding cross-disciplinary grant opportunities for faculty, and promising overseas partnerships, all of which meshed with their respective institutional vision and strengths. The study revealed that in 1995, The University of Pennsylvania initiated a planning process entitled “Agenda for Excellence,” which had as one of its primary goals, the enhancement of the university’s global position and international reputation both at home and overseas. It further revealed that today, all twelve of Penn's schools and virtually every academic program incorporates a global perspective as part of their curricula, and faculty in a wide variety of disciplines view international issues and comparative approaches as integral to their research agendas. This is because Leadership at the university has continually restated its commitment to this focus and has indicated in a variety of communications that global dimensions are becoming even more important as information and technology reduce the natural barriers of time and distance, resulting in the need for more globally educated graduates.

d. The Role of Faculty

The article identified the role of Faculty as central and critical to an institution’ embrace of globalization. It was specified that exemplary international programs and initiatives of higher educational institutions succeed or fail based on the capability of their faculty members, these faculty members have been recognized as their creative entrepreneurs. It was argued that Universities must against this backdrop create a team of dedicated faculty who are not locally minded, give them responsibility for initiatives, and then reward them for their superior efforts and results. The article identifies the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (UNC), through its University Center for International Studies (UCIS) which was recognized as an excellent example of an institution where emphasis is laid on the leading role of its faculty in developing programs of excellence.

e. Inter-wovenness of Student' Campus Community:

It was observed that students are central to the success of any university's attempt to globalize its campus and community, and students are the primary reason a university should embrace internationalization. Not only this, but as the University is a molding place for leaders and future leaders, the article identifies findings that also revealed that if students are to fully assume positions of leadership and responsibility in specific organizations and in society as a whole, then they must be prepared to deal with the global environment that confronts them today and will continue to challenge them in the future. It is recommended that both domestic and international students must be woven into any institution's "international fabric" if a genuinely globalized on-campus and community-wide environment is to be achieved. In pursuit of this objective, some of the policies identified are exceptional visiting scholar support, unique degree and non-degree certification options, distinctive overseas study agendas, exclusive international internships, innovative student scholarships, part-time job options in the international arena; outstanding cross-disciplinary grant opportunities for faculty, and promising overseas partnerships. The article identifies for example, Georgia Tech University as one institution that exemplifies this in many ways, with information that GTU has over 2,400 international students representing 100 countries. This comprises roughly thirteen percent of the total student population. Forty percent of all master level graduate students at GTU are international, as are 50 percent of doctoral candidates. The university supports these students through 33 internationally oriented clubs and organizations. Most of these organizations are designed to promote cultural interaction among all GTU students and the Atlanta community. ("Education at the University Level: What the "Markets" Want") The university also makes effective use of its international educational partnerships to recruit overseas students. One successful tactic in this regard is to promote GTU as an institution where one can get an additional "third" cultural experience (i.e., beyond one's home country and the United States) by studying at one of the university's partner institutions in Hong Kong, Europe, or South America [4]

f. Institutional Partnership:

Partnership is defined as a legal form of business operation between two or more individuals who share management and profit [6]. The federal government(s) recognizes several types of partnerships. The two most common are general and limited partnerships.

Global institutionalization thrives on partnership and alliance. These are critical components of international educational development which provides a global focus. No institution is an island. The value of university partnerships (whether they are developed by the university, or contained within various colleges, schools, departments or programs) with local, regional, national and international communities is well understood by leaders in higher education. The article supposes that partnerships or alliances can take on many forms including those with other institutions of education (within the United States and overseas), within a framework of a consortium of universities (again, within the United States and overseas), with a university and its alumni (both U.S. based and international), and with a university and various for-profit, not-for-profit, governmental, non-governmental, and other types of organizations. The list of possibilities is truly only limited by a university's vision and corresponding goals. In the report, Dr. William Bosher, Former Dean, School of Education, Virginia Commonwealth University postulates that "The focus of the university should not be location, location, location, but relation, relation, relation. A central ingredient to strong international programs is the establishment of meaningful relationships based on common values and goals and a sense of trust between partners. ("GLOBALIZATION OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION - AACSB") In today's globalized world this reality has never been more important."

g. Centralized and Decentralization of International Efforts:

Both centralized and decentralized dimensions of international efforts were the most prominent commonality among the institutions examined by the author of the article. Most successful institutions had a centralized "one-stop" office for administering, advising, coordinating, implementing, and maintaining all international activities. "On the other hand, it was apparent that while information on almost all international programs could be found in the centralized international office, most successful international programs were championed by a specific faculty (or individual) of a specific school, department, center or other decentralized branch of an institution." ("PHILIPPINE-QUALIFICATION-FRAMEWORK.docx - PHILIPPINE QUALIFICATION ...") ("PHILIPPINE-QUALIFICATION-FRAMEWORK.docx - PHILIPPINE QUALIFICATION ...") In general, innovative initiatives tended to have clearly designated individuals with known "creative" expertise who developed, promoted, managed, maintained and continually sought to improve a given program.

Such “champions” The key is to have an organizational structure that encourages and facilitates the exchange of information, ideas and ultimately knowledge.”

h. Branding of The University in The International Arena:

The article contains information from most university leaders interviewed who viewed their institutions as a brand, whose was built primarily by the people that make up its entire or extended community. This includes creative faculty, loyal students, proud alumni, committed partners, and visionary administrators. It highlighted that the more successful, globally focused universities tended to be those that proactively harnessed the emotional as well as the intellectual connections with all members of their extended communities. Such universities articulated worthy causes, communicated important outcomes and promised meaningful experiences worthy of one’s energies, time and allegiance. In other words, among great universities, an overarching reality is that success is not just about the education (the product), or the buildings (the infrastructure) it is about the people. (“Education at the University Level: What the “Markets” Want”).

3. RECOMMENDATIONS TOWARDS GLOBALISATION:

The following were identified from the article’s investigation, and they have been recommended as necessities for Globalisation of Higher Education:

- (i) Top level visionary underpinnings
- (ii) Development of deep-rooted entrepreneurial cultures that are international in scope
- (iii) The creation, transfer and use of knowledge is ongoing and evolving.
- (iv) Differentiating your institution’s programmes from others’ programs.
- (v) Institutions of higher education should seek ways to further connect their faculty, students and outside communities in a strategic infrastructure where ideas flow, new initiatives blossom, flexibility abounds, and global reputations expand. This supports the primary work of 21st century universities which is to seek Knowledge development and the commercialization of that knowledge in the international context.

4. CONCLUSION

The writer concluded his report with an important statement of awareness creation identified to be the most profound hallmark of the new millennium, that is, the ever-increasing interdependence of our world, specifically recommending that people who embrace Globalization will benefit the most. Secondly, that if not all, then most of the institution of higher education’s success comes from the people that develop, nurture, manage, consume and grow from the international experience offered by the institution. Hence the assertion that Globalization is here to stay which I concur with as well.

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